

Methods and Approaches of Teaching English

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Abstract: This article provides a lot of information about interactive methods of teaching English, methods used around the world. The methods given below can be used not only in higher education institutions but also in secondary schools.

Keywords: Methodology, grammar-translation, interaction, techniques, approaches, communicative method, game method.

English is a compulsory subject in elementary and secondary schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan. During this period, students receive basic knowledge of the English language, learn the alphabet, expand their vocabulary, and learn to read small texts.

The methodology of teaching English in schools is usually the same and is based on the curriculum approved by the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Almost all teachers most often use a communicative approach when teaching elementary school students. Nevertheless, in order to make the lessons more effective, some use additional techniques and approaches that make the lesson much more interesting and exciting.

In this section, we have explored examples of methods used around the world to make elementary English classes effective and at the same time interesting for students. Below are some examples of them:

Classical method

For many years, the classical method of teaching English in schools was employed. They are based on the grammar-translation technique. Each lesson/sub course is designed on a grammatical component in English that is taught in the student's native tongue.

The teacher engages with the students and explains the main points. Students then learn the rules, practice them, and complete assignments to reinforce them. With so much theory, however, students typically feel lost and fail to develop speaking skills. As a result, this method is only effective when paired with other methods, such as communication (Strekatova, 2020).

Communicative method

Today, the communicative method of teaching foreign languages is one of the most widely used throughout the world. Many people believe it is the most advanced and effective.

This method is a collection of strategies for teaching successful communication in a linguistic setting. The majority of them have already been utilized in the classroom. One of its key approaches is to imitate events from real life, aimed to inspire pupils to actively "speaking". At the same time, it is critical that the themes be timely and relevant to student's everyday lives and challenges. The students themselves - their responses, and reactions, determine the path of the lesson in communicative methods classes and so on. Because meaningful discussion happens on proper themes. Of course, speaking makes up the majority of the lessons, but reading and writing are also covered. In general, teachers do not speak but instead, listen and control the path of the class (Strekatova, 2020).

Glenn Doman Method

This is a popular method of teaching English in elementary schools. It is even being used to educate youngsters as young as 6-7. The method focuses on working with cards that include text or images. The teacher displays the card to the student and says the word. The student, who learns new vocabulary without hurrying, then repeats the procedure.

Despite his passive engagement in learning, the toddler finds it quite easy to acquire and memorize new words. Children have difficulty focusing. As a result, children fail to connect with texts and remember words. The Glen Doman method is popular among students and teachers worldwide since it needs little effort (Strekatova, 2020).

Game Method

Teaching English in elementary school using a game method aims to maintain the attention and interest of students in the lesson. In the lower grades, students are very mobile, active and emotional. Therefore, tasks in the form of a game allow you to direct the energy of students in the right direction and focus their attention on learning.

When playing a foreign language is not perceived as difficult and requires a lot of effort to learn. In the classroom, students are not afraid to make mistakes when

they complete assignments. At the same time, songs, cartoons, games with a competitive element can be included in the lesson, which will make the lesson even more exciting (Strekatova, 2020).

Zaitsev's Method

Features of teaching English in elementary school according to Zaitsev's method are that students use blocks with syllables and letters. With the help of them, they form words and thus memorize new phrases. The purpose of the approach is to show the algorithm for constructing words and sentences.

The cubes can be of different colors to make it easier for the child. Over time, the student tries to build colors and letters according to dictation. Such mini-dictations are effective, do not cause difficulties for children, and can be carried out even by parents.

These methods of teaching English in elementary school are not very popular. The bottom line is that after studying the topic, parsing texts, and memorizing new phrases, the teacher sets projects: play a scene, write a story, compose and conduct a dialogue, etc.

Special attention is given to the combined method, which combines different approaches and tasks from other methods. This approach introduces diversity and adapts the curriculum to the interests of the students. The combined technique does not have strict requirements. The teacher usually independently chooses methods and techniques that correspond to the specifics of his teaching and the interests of the children (Strekatova, 2020).

Interactive methods

Teaching English to kids and adults requires interactive learning. You and your child can benefit from a variety of activities if you undertake them together. Be creative and original. Make a collage or a poster, make crafts, and so forth. You may also plan workshops for you and your child, such as preparing a salad or cooking pizza, constructing soft toys, or participating in any activity together. Growing flowers, for example, may include creating a flowerbed or a mini-garden.

Interaction in English between a teacher (or a parent) and a child should always take place in real-life settings. This method assists children and adults in

indirectly learning the language while participating in various activities (Strekatova, 2020).

Project-based approach

Another effective way for teaching English is to base the learning process on projects and project activities. The approach was previously utilized mostly with high school students and professional people, but in the last ten years, instructors have begun to employ it with younger children and toddlers as well.

A research technique is the project method. It aims to improve linguistic abilities and creative thinking. After completing each course, students must work on a project and "defend" it by discussing its contents in English. For example, by expanding on themes such as "My favorite subject," "My family is...", or "In my room there is...", kids may express themselves about what is important to them.

It is a really interesting and enjoyable approach to practicing English with visuals and photographs, making it simpler to learn new vocabulary and phrases (Strekatova, 2020).

The natural approach

Students typically learn to speak before learning to write in a foreign language using this approach. The natural approach emphasizes spontaneous interactions in the target language. It necessitates either a simulation of real-life situations in a classroom context or actual interaction with foreigners. What is the most efficient way? Travel to another country for a vacation or a language course, establish some foreign acquaintances or find a native speaker teacher. This method is good for individual students or small groups, but it will not function in a chaotic setting. In this approach, the pupil should always be able to talk freely (Steven D., 1985).

References

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